

FEATURES OF A COMPETENCY APPROACH TO THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE NATIONAL CURRICULUM IN PRACTICE

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Abstract. *In this article, we discuss the scientific and methodological foundations for the implementation of the national curriculum on information technology in primary education, as well as the discussion of the draft national curriculum by the Republican Inspectorate of Education.*

Keywords: *consideration, technology, goals, curriculum, educational standards, primary education, mathematics, knowledge and skills.*

The block-module of Exact Sciences covers the subjects of Mathematics, Computer Science and Information Technology and ensures the interaction of these subjects.

The importance of Informatics and information technologies and mathematics, sciences are important in the formation of mathematical culture of students, scientific accuracy in mathematics, the formation of their worldviews, the solution of practical problems necessary in the development of their thinking, functional erudition, logical thinking, as well as the formation of a common culture of a person.

The extent to which the internal motivation of the student is formed plays an important role in the analysis of his interest in the Exact Sciences, awareness of environmental problems and knowledge of making important decisions in solving it, as well as its impact on the natural and social environment.

It consists in mastering the methods and means of Information Technology, the formation of problem-solving skills, the development of skills for applying, analyzing and modifying information models of real objects and processes.

It consists of developing intellectual and creative abilities through algorithmic and computational thinking and computer models, considering the implementation of information processes through computer technology, working with computer systems and models, studying information protection methods, modeling using interactive computer models, formalizing and developing a project systematic approach.

At the same time, in the direction of specialized education, it is advisable to comprehensively develop the talent and abilities of young people, to support their aspirations to master science and to train them in the spirit of loyalty to the motherland as a harmonious, physically and spiritually healthy person, expanding the topics in the sciences.

Educational technology in the Steam Exact Sciences block module aims to carry out Educational Research in lesson and extracurricular activities, to carry out experiments, to educate their design-oriented creativity, to develop their interest in creating innovations in showing the knowledge, skills and competencies that students occupy with everyday life.

In the implementation of this technology, tasks such as creating projects for the construction of various technical devices by students, creating a mock-up of the device based on the project and using it in practice, finding its shortcomings and eliminating it are performed.

In the block-module of Exact Sciences, it is considered one of the main tasks before the teacher to instill in the minds of the younger generation the students logical thinking and work with practical tasks that are designed to work with tasks corresponding to the requirements of the International Assessment Program (PISA, TIMSS), aimed at forming practical skills.

Of great importance in the teaching of exact subjects is not only their integration with the subjects, which are part of their mutual internal, but also External, that is, related block-modules. In particular, it is important that they interact closely with the following areas of science:

Competencies, which are formed through native language and literature, foreign languages, play an important role in the development of creative thinking of students in teaching natural and Economic Sciences, in the formation of competencies to fluently express their views in writing and verbally, in the correct application of scientific terms and in teaching free communication in the process of discussions.

History the subject of study is also directly linked to natural and Economic Sciences. Historical data is of great importance in showing the impact of the achievements of science on the development of production areas, economic-social relations and the state of the environment.

The subject of mathematics-education has a great place in the development of a person's intellect, attention, in the upbringing of determination and will to achieve the intended goal, in the provision of algorithmic-style discipline and in the expansion of his thinking. Mathematics is the basis of knowledge of the universe, and tevarak-the disclosure of the specific laws of the surrounding events and phenomena, is important in the development of production, science and technology.

Informatics and the teaching of the subject of AT study takes into account the priority of digital economics for further development in scientific and technical terms, serves to develop the competence and culture of students of general secondary educational institutions in the field of digital technologies and the ability to think critically and develop creative information and communication competencies. Together with the understanding of natural phenomena and basic physical processes, in the development of techniques and technologies, Informatics and the laws of it are practiced

The growing importance of mastering and putting into practice new knowledge to create innovative products in the rapidly developing digital age is one of the important factors determining the competitiveness of the national economy and the effectiveness of national security strategies.

In the era of globalization, in accordance with the requirements of the labor market, certain models of thinking are needed to implement the issue of raising young people who can cope with non-standard issues based on the approach of creativity, such models of thinking in children are formed at school age.

The widespread use of the achievements of the activities of Science and innovation in the world education system, the consistent and sustainable development of all spheres of society and state Life is an important factor in establishing a worthy future of the country. With high professional competence, competitive staff training, innovation in education, the wide introduction of modern, interactive and creative teaching techniques play an important role in the development

of students' abilities that can carry out scientific research based on indicators such as motivational, cognitive, operational, reflexive and self-assessment.

In an innovative economy, a high level of knowledge of modern ICT, the ability to master and develop digital technologies are considered as an extremely important factor.

Informatics and its educational subject - a component of general secondary educational disciplines, allows students to put knowledge about the basics of science into practice, master general principles, specific skills of the formation of human activities, types of general, digital and material culture, and also find and implement innovative solutions to practical problems based on digital technologies.

Competence in working with information refers to the importance of information related to the world around us explains;

the main concepts under study are: information, algorithm, model and forms an idea of their properties;

self-control, self-awareness, independent in educational activities makes decisions;

set, set element, part set, belonging, sets uses concepts such as intersection and Union, definition, axiom, theorem, proof at the base level;

gives examples showing the correctness of the reasoning; natural number, Prime and complex numbers, number division, integer, simple uses concepts such as fraction, decimal, rational number, arithmetic square root, irrational number;

performs actions on rational numbers and special-looking irrational numbers; compares numbers;

rounding numbers; simple and decimal places sort numbers in view;

performs uncomplicated substitutions in the calculations of the values of numerical expressions containing natural and negative whole levels;

performs uncomplicated substitutions of Whole expressions: opens brackets, brings similar terms, renders the common factor out of brackets;

in simplifying the calculations of the values of expressions, the short multiplication uses formulas;

complex of expressions involving fractional-linear and Square Roots performs non-substitutions;

columnar and circular diagrams, data tables, middle arithmetic, median, largest and smallest value of a numerical series, scatter, use their concepts at the base level;

reads, explains and replaces information given in the form of a table and diagram representing surrounding processes, sees quantities that change randomly in the environment, including measurement results; complies with the requirements and rules of Information Ethics in the process of computer programs and work on the Internet;

purposefully searches for lost information, compares individual parts. From the hope, in the formation of communicative competencies, it is necessary to correctly perceive, interpret and teach to communicate terms related to the Exact Sciences in the formation of the skills of independent, creative thinking, written and oral fluency in mastering the state language, foreign languages.

Effective riv of competence of work with information in the teaching of subjects

In the formation of self-development competence, it is necessary to have universal qualities, love the motherland, acquire legal, economic knowledge, strive for innovations and, on

the basis of acquired theoretical knowledge, to make independent decisions, be aware of progressive and innovative changes in society and be able to use them in everyday life.

Civic duty in the formation of socio-emotional and civic competence consists in acquiring knowledge about social and political development, emergencies, environmental problems and understanding artistic, scientific and artistic works and the development of organizational qualities in their preservation. Concept of development of the teaching of Informatics and information technology concept of the development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2035, 'According to the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 5712 of April 29, 2019, "the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", the concept of development of the industry of Uzbekistan until 2025 and the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Developed on the basis of the tasks set out in Mirziyoev's appeal to the Supreme Assembly on January 24, 2020.

2. The concept sets out the main trends in the development of the teaching of Informatics and science AT in the system of public education.

Including: ensuring compliance with the international requirements for the training of qualified personnel on the world market, taking into account national characteristics and reforms carried out in the country, from the experience of calculating the main link of general education in the educational system of highly industrialized United Kingdom, France, Germany, USA, Izrail, South Korea, people's Republic of China and other developed;

development and implementation of the Digital Uzbekistan – 2030 program, which provides for the renewal of all sectors of the economy on the basis of digital technologies;

formation of enrichment and competence of the skills acquired by students studying in secondary schools in order to receive education in an informed society, live and work in a digitized environment in the future;

Informatics and it science ensure compliance with the requirements of the state educational standard with the international requirements for the quality of education and training of personnel;

practical implementation of qualification requirements for graduates of general secondary educational institutions in Computer Science and it;

strengthening the methodological and material and technical base of public educational institutions;

qualitatively updating the content of Informatics and it science, as well as improving the teaching methodology;

development of variative learning modules in the teaching of Informatics and it science;

development of a methodology for involving students in project and educational research activities;

wide introduction of effective forms, methods and means of educating students on the basis of national, universal and spiritual values into the educational process;

the integration of Computer Science and it with general education and the organization of vocational orientation of students;

introduction of modern methods and directions of classroom and extracurricular education in Informatics and it in the education of student-youth.

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